

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

31/10/2024

Abstract

This is the initial report of the requirement gathering and analysis process for enhancing the existing European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Core services, which are central to the EOSC Beyond project. The aim is to ensure these services meet the evolving needs of their stakeholders, encompassing end-users, service providers, and EOSC Nodes. Through rigorous engagement with various stakeholders and leveraging insights from previous EOSC initiatives, the document identifies existing gaps and proposes specific enhancements to align with the long-term objectives of the EOSC community.

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the comprehensive requirement gathering and analysis process for enhancing the existing European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Core services, which are central to the EOSC Beyond project. The aim is to ensure these services meet the evolving needs of their stakeholders, encompassing end-users, service providers, and EOSC Nodes. Through rigorous engagement with various stakeholders and leveraging insights from previous EOSC initiatives, the document identifies existing gaps and proposes specific enhancements to align with the long-term objectives of the EOSC community.

This initial report will also serve as a guide to kickstart Work Packages 8 and 9, focusing on the development of the next generation of EOSC Core services. It presents a systematic methodology for identifying and analysing enhancements required for Core services' functionality improvement and their integration with Pilot Nodes. The methodology emphasises iterative requirement gathering for Core Services and recognition of requirements relevant to the Core Services from user stories and requirements relevant to the creation of EOSC Nodes Federation.

Key findings from the gap analysis indicate the need for a federated architecture that supports seamless interoperability across various infrastructure services. The conclusions drawn from this analysis underscore the necessity for a harmonised approach to service development that addresses both current and future demands for scalability and flexibility in resource sharing. This report summarises the recommendations for implementing advanced technological solutions that support robust service integration within the EOSC Nodes Federation.

1. Introduction

Requirement gathering and analysis are essential in the software development process as they ensure new solutions effectively meet user needs and bridge existing system gaps. This *Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report* plays a crucial role in the EOSC Beyond project, which seeks to deliver innovative EOSC Core technical solutions for the EOSC Nodes Federation. By engaging multiple stakeholders, the project aims to maintain a user-centric approach while keeping the broader goals of the federation in view. Systematic identification of requirements helps pinpoint specific needs and deficiencies in the current technical landscape, facilitating well-planned enhancements. This approach incorporates feedback from key stakeholders and considers specific user types (end-users, service providers and Nodes) to inform the design of new functionalities. Recognising these gaps allows the project to develop targeted solutions that enhance the functionality and efficiency of the Core services and to introduce new capabilities to support more complex user scenarios. This report lays the groundwork for the activities in WP8 and WP9, focusing on delivering enhanced Core Services that not only meet current demands but also align with the long-term goals of the EOSC community, therefore fostering improved collaboration and resource sharing among Nodes.

It is important to highlight that, for the purposes of this report, the terms platform, core services are defined as those developed during previous EOSC projects such as EOSC-Hub, EOSC Future and EOSC Enhance. The gaps and therefore requirements captured are focused on the capabilities offered by the service providers that are part of the EOSC Beyond Consortium and are committed to developing them further .

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document

This initial report summarises the outcomes of WP7 in the EOSC Beyond project, which focuses on designing the next generation of existing EOSC Core services. To accomplish this, a systematic approach (presented in the Methodology section) for requirement gathering and analysis has been established and consistently applied through iterations, gathering inputs from relevant stakeholders. The primary scope of this document is to conduct an analysis of the existing Core services, specifically focusing on identifying areas for enhancement to ensure that the evolution of these services is grounded in identified needs and the improvements planned in the project's Description of Action ([DoA](#)). While this analysis primarily targets these services, it also incorporates user-centric, high-level inputs applicable to other technical work packages that deliver new core services, such as the Execution Framework. Understanding these connections is important for enhancing services in WP8 and WP9. This comprehensive approach ensures that the identified gaps and requirements effectively align with user needs and overarching project objectives.

The primary goal of this document is to conduct a gap analysis of the existing Core services based on the inputs and requirements gathered, leading to specifications and designs for the planned work in Work Packages 8 (WP8) and 9 (WP9).

Thus, the purpose of this report is to serve as a strategic tool to guide the enhancement of Core services within the EOSC Nodes Federation, facilitating improved service integration and functionality tailored to user and stakeholder needs.

1.2. Structure of the document

This report is organised into five main sections, each serving a distinct purpose:

1. **Introduction:** This section.
2. **Methodology:** this section presents the methodology to deliver this report's findings, using the requirement gathering process established in WP7. The process focuses on collecting structured inputs from various stakeholders to ensure development efforts align with the needs of the EOSC community and project goals, especially regarding existing Core services.
3. **Gap Analysis for the Platform as a Whole:** presents an overview of the gap analysis conducted for the EOSC Core Platform as it was delivered by EOSC Future¹ and is currently deployed in its testing and validating environment the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, summarising the key findings from the gathered use cases and requirements collected in the project, like these provided by the Pilot Nodes participating in WP15 ('Co-design and initial integration of EOSC Nodes and Data Spaces'). It identifies both strengths and areas for improvement across the platform, setting the foundation for subsequent, Core service-focused gap analyses.
4. **Gap Analysis and Requirement Capture for Each Core Service:** outlines the identified deficiencies, proposed enhancements and user needs pertinent to enhancing their functionality and interoperability within the EOSC framework.
5. **Conclusions:** synthesises the insights presented in this report, reinforcing the importance of the findings in guiding the future development of the EOSC Core services in the scope of WP8 and WP9.

2. Methodology

2.1. Introduction

The results presented are part of the comprehensive approach to requirement collection and analysis within the EOSC Beyond project. Due to the complexity of the EOSC Federation concept, the technical activities required to deliver its first pilot version were divided into four development areas, discussed later in this chapter. All requirements were gathered using a consistent methodology and analysed within their respective areas. This deliverable focuses on the requirements specific to the EOSC Core Capabilities Area. However, it also maintains a strong connection to the Node-specific Requirements area, dedicating sections to summarise findings from these requirements. This area was thoroughly described and reported in deliverable D15.1: Service Integration Plans of the Data Spaces and EOSC

¹ <https://eoscfuture.eu/results/>

Nodes². The needs and requirements outlined there have been translated into specific requirements for the Core Services and are presented as such in this deliverable.

2.2. EOSC Beyond Requirement Gathering Process

The requirements gathering process is designed to ensure that the development of Core services within the EOSC Beyond project aligns with community needs and supports integration with various services. This subsection outlines the key stages and channels involved in this process. The requirements gathering is structured around four main development areas: EOSC Core capabilities, Core services adapters, execution framework, and node-specific requirements. Each category addresses requirements pertinent to a specific functional area of the EOSC Nodes Federation.

- **EOSC Core Capabilities** - requirements focussing on enhancements for existing core services. These should be derived from the community's understanding of what the services should offer and the necessary development for integration with Nodes.
- **Core Services Adapters** - requirements for developing adapters to facilitate easier integration between EOSC Core services and new communities joining the EOSC Federation.
- **Execution Framework** - requirements focussing on delivering the EOSC Execution Framework components. This reflects the community's perspective on what the execution framework should offer in terms of capabilities and integration.
- **Node-specific Requirements** - these requirements address the needs for implementing EOSC Nodes for specific use cases and their integration with EOSC Core services.

It is important to understand that the same technology (and services based on it) can be a part of multiple development areas. The WP7 scope focuses on the EOSC Core Capabilities development area and services with their functionalities connected to it

The EOSC Beyond's requirement gathering process has been implemented in Jira (a ticket tracking solution) along with roadmapping process and software delivery and QA processes, as all of them are interconnected and serve the goal of the delivery of the project's outcomes.

2.2.1. Stakeholders and requirement gathering channels

The requirements gathering process involves engaging multiple stakeholders and utilising various channels to ensure input from the broadest possible EOSC community. At the project's outset, the focus was on stakeholders closely connected to the project participants

² Lechowska-Winiarz, K., Wilk, R., & Gutiérrez, M. (2024). EOSC Beyond D15.1 Service integration plans of the Data Spaces and EOSC Nodes (1 Under EC Review). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13152335>.

and their channels. Thus, the inputs for this deliverable come from original project plans and the following stakeholders within the EOSC Beyond project:

- **DoA (Description of Action)** - reference to the overall project description, defining scope, objectives and expected outcomes.
- **Product Teams** - internal teams responsible for the development and enhancement of EOSC services.
- **Pilot Nodes (Beyond)** - Pilot Nodes within the EOSC Beyond project provide practical insights into what is needed to enhance the services.
- **Technical Coordination Board** - a governing body that ensures technical requirements align with the overall technical roadmap of the project.

In the further course of the project, the requirement gathering and analysis process will engage a wider group of identified stakeholders:

- **Science Clusters (Oscars³)** - large research communities contribute requirements based on the needs of their domain-specific services and tools.
- **Research Infrastructures** - infrastructure providers that facilitate research across various disciplines provide input on the technical and service requirements.
- **EOSC Association** - the EOSC Association may provide strategic insights and ensure that gathered requirements align with the broader goals of the EOSC ecosystem.

And use following channels to gather and respond to the requirements:

- **Workshops (Service Providers)** - workshops involving service providers, where the needs and challenges from the perspective of those offering services are discussed.
- **Workshops (Consumers)** - these workshops focus on the needs of end-users (researchers, research communities, etc.)
- **Workshops (Thematic)** - these workshops address specific themes or emerging "hot topics" within the research community, ensuring EOSC stays relevant to cutting-edge issues.
- **Dedicated surveys** - to reach a wider audience, dedicated surveys will be disseminated using the project's channel

2.2.2. Scope of WP7 - EOSC Core Capabilities

The scope for WP7 focuses on enhancing the existing EOSC Core Services based on community feedback (already mentioned in the list of the stakeholders), aiming to integrate services more effectively across the EOSC Federation. The scope includes the following capabilities:

³ <https://oscars-project.eu/>

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- Platform (as a whole)
- AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure)
- PID (Persistent Identifier) Service
- Resource Catalogue (Service + Research Product Catalogue)
- Marketplace (with Resource Discovery Hub included)
- Explore
- User Dashboard
- Order Management
- Monitoring Service
- Accounting for Services
- Accounting for Research Products
- Helpdesk
- Interoperability Framework Registry
- Messaging Service

2.2.3. Requirement Handling Workflow

The iterative nature of the WP7 process ensures that every two weeks, the gathered requirements are processed and analysed through the following steps:

1. Selection - identify which requirements need to be analysed.
2. Team analysis - determine if the requirements are clear, complete and ready for further evaluation.
3. Team allocation - assign the requirement to a team for analysis and estimation of the required effort.
4. Specification development - translate the requirement into a specification, including a definition of done, actions required and acceptance criteria.
5. Acceptance - decide if the requirement is viable for development.
6. Prioritisation and dependencies - assign priorities and dependencies, feeding this information into the roadmap planning process.
7. Validation - for requirements requiring substantial effort, validation is sought from the TCB.
8. Assignment to product teams - once validated, the requirement is handed over to product teams for development, testing and release management.
9. Deployed in the Core Innovation Sandbox - Integration Environment for verification
10. Release in the Core Innovation Sandbox - Pre-Production Environment
11. Invite stakeholders to test and provide feedback.

Using the approach outlined in this chapter, WP7 aims to deliver outputs in the form of requirements and corresponding designs. These outputs will serve as the development specifications for work conducted in WP8 and WP9, the development work packages focused on EOSC Core Capabilities within the EOSC Beyond Project.

3. Gap Analysis for the EOSC Core Platform and its community use cases

This section focuses on the EOSC Platform as a whole, while also directly correlating with the needs identified in section 4. It identifies the current state of play, focusing on strengths and potential areas of improvement, particularly in relation to user requirements and service integration. The identified gaps will showcase the roadmap for further development of the EOSC Core services, ensuring alignment with the stakeholders needs and capabilities and the integration of new functionalities into the EOSC Federation, with the ultimate goal to deliver an enhanced EOSC Platform at the end of the project.

The EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox by EOSC Beyond is a pre-production environment of the EOSC Platform that acts as a testing and staging environment - equipped with advanced automation tools - for EOSC Core service providers, EOSC Exchange service providers and EOSC Nodes to use as part of the integration process with EOSC.

This chapter presents two main categories for gap analysis. The first analysis is based on community insights from the Pilot Nodes in WP15. The second section summarises the technical expertise and experience contributed by the project and its partners. In summary, the first section translates the requirements and needs expressed by the pilot nodes into requirements for the EOSC Platform. The second section provides insights from technical experts participating in the project, consolidating the goals set in the DoA and the gap analysis conducted by the development teams.

3.1. Pilot Nodes Use-Cases Breakdown

The EOSC Beyond project aims to establish a pilot of the EOSC federated infrastructure that integrates diverse services and resources across European research institutions. The integration of Pilot Nodes via the EOSC Integration Sandbox is essential to achieving this objective, with each Node providing unique requirements based on real-world research needs. However, the analysis of user journeys also reveals functional and technical gaps that must be addressed to ensure proper service delivery, interoperability, and scalability across the federation.

The key requirements to achieve this and the potential gaps for the EOSC Platform from the perspective of each Pilot Node are presented in Appendix 1. Below, a general summary provides an overview of key high-level requirements common to all nodes to achieve their goals. These requirements reference the EOSC Core services as an integrated platform and specifically refer to the services responsible for fulfilling the goals of the pilot nodes'.

- Federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) - Nodes require seamless Single Sign-On (SSO) through federated AAI, enabling users to access various EOSC services across institutions without managing multiple credentials.

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- Resource discovery and ordering - Integration with the EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace is essential to discover and order resources, including compute, storage and other digital services.
- Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) - Nodes require PID services to track, identify, and cite digital objects and research outputs reliably over the long term, ensuring proper data management and reusability.
- Data Transfer and File Sharing - Secure, scalable, and efficient data transfer services between Nodes are essential, particularly for managing large datasets and ensuring collaborative work across Nodes.
- Service monitoring and SLA management - Real-time service monitoring and comprehensive SLA reporting are necessary for maintaining high service standards. Nodes require integrated systems to track performance and fulfilment of service agreements.
- Execution Framework - Support for containerised and cloud-based services for the deployment of advanced scientific tools and workflows. Scalable environments are required to execute complex tasks, including data analysis and simulations.
- FAIR Data compliance in data discovery - Nodes need integration with EOSC resource catalogues to ensure compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles, enhancing data discoverability and usability across the federation.
- Helpdesk integration - A unified helpdesk system is required, integrated with EOSC, to address technical issues and user queries efficiently across services, ensuring consistent and accessible support.

In addition to the outlined requirements, several technical challenges and gaps must be addressed to provide effective integration and service delivery within and across federation:

- AAI integration challenges - Integrating local AAI systems with the federated EOSC AAI may pose difficulties, particularly in ensuring secure user authentication across multiple institutional frameworks. Technical solutions are needed to harmonise these systems.
- Interoperability of core and exchange services - Achieving full interoperability between EOSC Core and Exchange services, such as compute, storage, and orchestration, across different Nodes is challenging. This involves ensuring that resources from multiple providers can be effectively combined and orchestrated to support complex workflows, which may require additional development to align different systems and services.
- Service monitoring and SLA reporting - Not all Nodes possess fully developed service monitoring systems. Integrating local systems with EOSC's Monitoring service, alongside real-time synchronisation and comprehensive SLA reporting, presents significant technical complexities.

- **Data transfer and scalability** - Efficient scaling of data transfer services is a challenge, particularly when managing large datasets between Nodes. Providing high-speed, reliable data transfer across different storage systems and computing environments could require enhanced infrastructure and protocols.
- **Containerisation and cloud integration** - While container services are essential for many Nodes, ensuring seamless deployment across various cloud environments may prove complex. The orchestration and scaling of these services between local infrastructures and EOSC's cloud framework may require more advanced solutions.
- **Persistent Identifier (PID) management** - The management of PIDs across Nodes can present inconsistencies, as different Nodes may follow varying standards for PID registration and management. These processes should be harmonised to ensure consistent tracking and management of digital objects.
- **Helpdesk and support integration** - Full integration of local helpdesk systems with the EOSC helpdesk could be inhibited by differences in ticket management, workflows and communication standards. A standardised, federated support infrastructure is needed for effective problem resolution.

The following chapters elaborate these high-level requirements and gaps in more technical terms. More details on the federation challenge, identified use cases, user stories and requirements that follow can be found in the deliverable D15.1: Service integration plans of the Data Spaces and EOSC Nodes.

3.2. Requirements for federation of autonomous Nodes

The following section outlines the high-level gaps identified by the project's DoA, product teams and experts.

3.2.1. Interoperability Aspects

In order to provide better support for interoperability, the following features should be available in each component of the platform to allow Nodes and Services to integrate with the platform itself.

- **External Interfaces for Inter-Node Communication:** Even though components within a Node are tightly integrated, the Node itself should expose standardised interfaces for communication with other Nodes. This can be achieved via:
 - **REST APIs:** Nodes expose APIs that enable data sharing or task delegation across Nodes.
 - **Message Service:** Use a message Service (e.g., EOSC Messaging Service) or event-driven systems to notify other Nodes when a relevant change or event occurs. This is useful when Nodes need to work in coordination.

- **Data Exchange Format:** Ensure that Nodes communicate using standard data formats (e.g., JSON, XML, or Protocol Buffers) to maintain consistency across the system.
- **Service Contracts and Versioning:** To ensure smooth interaction between Nodes, establish service contracts and versioning mechanisms. This allows for future upgrades or changes in the interfaces without breaking compatibility between Nodes.

3.2.2. Add support for national, regional and thematic Nodes

In order to be able to support the notion of Nodes, each component of the core should be able to either be easily deployed or offered as a service for each Node. Similarly each component should provide the necessary interoperability options so that it is able to exchange data with its peers as required.

Each service within a Node should be designed as an independent service while the whole Node should operate as a tightly integrated set of capabilities. This enables the following options for each Node:

- **Easy Deployment:** Each component should be easily deployable independently. This gives flexibility in updating, scaling, or replacing individual components without affecting the entire Node.
- **As-a-Service Offering:** Each component can be offered as a service within the Node itself or even exposed as a service to other Nodes.

3.2.3. Support for a Federation of Nodes

The previous architecture, where a central Node integrates with national, regional, or thematic Nodes, indeed imposed limitations by funnelling researchers through a single, central portal. This approach can disrupt researchers' workflows, forcing them to adapt to a centralised system rather than letting them continue with their preferred tools and processes.

To overcome this, a federated architecture will be implemented, where Nodes act as equal peers, offering diverse capabilities while allowing researchers to access resources across the network without needing to go through a central hub.

In a federated system, each Node (whether national, regional, or thematic) is an autonomous entity with its own resources and capabilities.

- Rather than having one Node through which all resources are accessed, every Node has the ability to share and access resources across the network without relying on a single point of entry.
- Nodes communicate and collaborate with each other as equal peers, allowing decentralised resource discovery, access and integration into existing workflows.

- **Distributed Search and Discovery:** Researchers can access resources from any Node, either directly or via a search function that spans across all Nodes. This can be achieved using peer-to-peer discovery mechanisms or a distributed search index.
- **Autonomy of Nodes:** Each Node retains autonomy over its own resources, user interface and internal architecture. This means Nodes can be specialised for regional, national, or thematic purposes while still participating in the larger federated network.
- **Resource Federation:** Each Node exposes resources that can be shared across the federation. This could include data sets, computing capabilities, analysis tools, or other services.

4. Gap Analysis and Requirement Capture for Each Core Component.

This section of the report focuses on the gap analysis of each individual capability within the EOSC core and how each one will contribute to addressing the key gaps identified for the platform as a whole as described in the previous section. Each gap identified is presented and broken down to one or more requirements to be analysed further and selected for development by each team as part of work in WorkPackage 8 and 9.

4.1. AAI

The following section highlights key gaps in the EOSC Federated AAI and outlines actionable requirements to address them. The primary challenges revolve around inconsistent handling of advanced authentication methods, lack of native OpenID Connect support, fragmented authorisation approaches, and interoperability with emerging data spaces like SIMPL. Additionally, there are inefficiencies in user and access provisioning across infrastructures. The outlined requirements focus on enhancing security, interoperability, and consistency across EOSC Nodes, to ensure seamless AAI integration in line with evolving standards.

4.1.1. GAP: Inconsistent handling of advanced authentication mechanisms

When a service in one EOSC Node requires stronger authentication (e.g., Multi-Factor Authentication - MFA), it can signal this requirement using standard mechanisms according to the authentication protocol. The AAI should prioritise the enhanced authentication capabilities provided by the user's home Identity Provider (IdP) whenever possible. In cases where the home IdP does not support such capabilities, the AAI should provide the required authentication strength.

To enable this functionality:

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- Support for Advanced Authentication Methods: EOSC Nodes must support strong authentication methods like Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) or Passwordless Authentication to meet varying security needs.
- Home Identity Provider Preference: The AAI service should prioritise the use of the advanced authentication methods available by a user's home Identity Provider. If the home Identity Provider supports such methods, it should be preferred to maintain consistency with institutional policies and to streamline the user experience.
- Fallback Provision: In cases where the home Identity Provider does not support any advanced authentication mechanisms, the AAI must offer its own mechanism to fulfil the requirement for stronger authentication. This fallback mechanism should be secure and configurable to support different methods such as One-Time Passwords (OTPs) or hardware tokens.
- Interoperability Across Nodes: The AAI service must ensure interoperability across EOSC Nodes, translating authentication context indicators between protocols like OpenID Connect and SAML2.

ID: WP7-R68, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Seamless Advanced Authentication Mechanisms

4.1.2. GAP: EOSC federated AAI lacks native support for OpenID Connect

The reliance on SAML2 for connecting to the EOSC AAI Federation requires a protocol translation layer for OpenID Connect AAI services, complicating the integration process.

To enable this functionality:

- The AAI services should implement support for [OpenID Federation](#) to facilitate native OpenID Connect and OAuth 2.0 flows. By leveraging the trust infrastructure defined in the OpenID Federation specification, AAI services can dynamically establish trust. This will allow EOSC Nodes to securely interact, leveraging Trust Anchors to validate membership and compliance without manual or bilateral trust agreements.

ID: WP7-R69, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for OpenID Connect Federations

4.1.3. GAP: Lack of Harmonised Approach to Authorisation

The current approach to authorisation across research infrastructures is fragmented, resulting in inconsistencies in how user attributes and resource capabilities are managed and enforced across different services. This gap presents challenges in efficiently sharing resources, ensuring traceability and maintaining security across EOSC Nodes. Additionally, the complexity of managing authorisation policies across multiple infrastructures, and the difficulty of making consistent authorisation decisions when resources are distributed across various sources, exacerbate these challenges.

To address this gap:

- **Support for Advanced Authorisation Mechanisms:** The AAI must implement advanced, harmonised authorisation mechanisms that consistently handle both user attributes (e.g., institutional affiliation, identity assurance, group memberships and role information) and resource capabilities. These mechanisms should account for the aggregation of authorisation-related information from multiple sources and support a flexible and efficient approach to managing authorisation decisions, even when the required data is distributed across infrastructures.
- **Interoperability Across EOSC Nodes:** A harmonised approach to authorisation must ensure interoperability across EOSC Nodes by using common standards and frameworks, as defined by the AARC Blueprint Architecture and accompanying guidelines. This will enable efficient, secure, and consistent sharing of federated resources while ensuring that authorisation decisions and policies can be enforced uniformly, regardless of the complexity or distribution of the authorisation information.

ID: WP7-R70, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for Advanced Authorisation Mechanisms

4.1.4. GAP: AAI Interoperability with SIMPL-based Data Spaces

SIMPL-based data spaces utilise a diverse range of identification, authentication, and authorisation mechanisms, including decentralised identity models. A study should be conducted to analyse integration points between the EOSC Federated AAI and SIMPL-based data spaces. This study will focus on evaluating SIMPL's Identification, Authentication and Authorization (IAA) framework and identifying pathways for interoperability.

ID: WP7-R71, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Integration Analysis of SIMPL IAA Framework with EOSC Federated AAI

4.1.5. GAP: Lack of Standardised User and Access Provisioning

The EOSC Federated AAI currently lacks a standardised approach for user and access provisioning and deprovisioning across services. This inconsistency hampers efficient user management and resource allocation.

To address this gap:

- The AAI will implement a proof of concept to demonstrate user and access provisioning and deprovisioning across different services. The investigation will focus on mechanisms based on standards (e.g. System for Cross-domain Identity Management - SCIM) to facilitate consistent and secure user management practices across services.

ID: WP7-R72, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Proof of Concept for User and Access Provisioning

4.2. Accounting for research products

The Accounting for Research Products, offered by the OpenAIRE UsageCounts service⁴, is an event tracking service that provides indicators on how research outputs, such as datasets, software, and publications, are used across multiple repositories where multiple copies of their files may have been deposited. Accurate usage accounting helps stakeholders, including researchers, funders, and institutions to understand the value, impact, and lifecycle of research products. This section provides a gap analysis of the current state of accounting for research products by analysing the Description of the Action (DoA) and the practical implementation by Pilot Nodes.

Platforms like OpenAIRE's Usage Counts service use tools (such as Matomo) to track how often research outputs are viewed via websites and downloaded from these, by implementing the Make Data Count standard. The UsageCounts Service implements a three-level architecture that aggregates usage data about research products and provides surrogate reporting to consumers:

- **Event collection:**
 - *Push-mode:* real-time tracking of access and download events via embedded tracking codes in repository websites; the actions of viewing a record or downloading the underlying files are tracked and sent as "events" to OpenAIRE UsageCounts, identified via time-stamp and persistent identifier (e.g. DOI);
 - *Pull-mode:* UsageCounts collects event data from similar systems (e.g. IRUS-UK).
- **Event aggregation:** events about the same persistent identifier, possibly coming from different repositories/data sources, are aggregated to provide overall usage summaries;
- **Reporting:** The data collected is used to generate reports that help repository managers and stakeholders understand how often research outputs are accessed

4.2.1. GAP: Lack of aggregated usage statistics for organisations available in the Graph

- **Current state:** usage data is made available to users via reports at the level of the research products, but the overall counting at the level of the organisation is not visible
- **Improvement needed:** UsageCounts should provide access to reporting schemes per organisation, e.g. totals per university X.
- **Actions:** design and implementation of the functionality

⁴ <https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/>

ID: WP7-R128, Requestor: D5.1 Evolution of the services in the current EOSC Platform

4.2.2. GAP: Limited Focus on Research Product Lifecycle

- **Current State:** OpenAIRE UsageCounts tracks views and downloads of research outputs according to Make Data Count specifications; for this reason, it cannot capture indicators about the reuse of products, e.g. “processing a dataset”.
- **Improvement Needed:** in order to track and quantify the full lifecycle of research products, including their reuse, OpenAIRE UsageCounts should be upgraded to collect events on product reuse.
- **Actions:** To this aim, MakeDataCount specifications should be update to include “reuse” events and other services than repositories, e.g. data analytics made eligible for producing and sending such events. As things stand, EOSC Beyond cannot deliver the extension, as it would require the involvement of the MakeDataCount working group and the identification of service providers willing to implement the functionality.

ID: WP7-R129, Requestor: user communities in RDA

4.3. Accounting for services

The Accounting for Services system is responsible for collecting, aggregating, and exchanging the metrics between different infrastructures, providers, and projects. It lacks support for proper integration with the Service Registries and multiple nodes simultaneously to be able to associate services with their accounting data. Similarly it would be useful to collect quota and capacity information so as to be able to to provide smarter reports for each Node, Project, community etc.

4.3.1. GAP: Be able to associate Service Accounting Data with EOSC Profiles.

The Accounting Service is designed to streamline metric collection, aggregation, and exchange across diverse infrastructures, providers and projects. Currently, it does not have a direct interface with the Service Catalogue, so while the service provides valuable accounting metrics, there is no straightforward way to automatically associate these metrics into the EOSC Profiles for services listed in the Catalogue.

To facilitate this feature:

- The Accounting Service should augment its REST API to communicate with the EOSC Profiles to retrieve detailed user information, such as project assignments, installations mappings, and roles associations, allowing for usage data presentation to specific users and their activities.
- The EOSC Service Catalogue must be enhanced to accept, display, and regularly update accounting data, enabling users to track and visualise their service usage effectively across projects and resources.

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

- Robust API-level authentication and authorization mechanisms are essential to securely transfer data between systems, ensuring proper mapping of users to their accounting metrics while maintaining data integrity and privacy.

ID: WP7-R102, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Integrate with the Service Catalogue to allow Accounting data for services to be introduced in the EOSC Profiles.

4.3.2. GAP: Services grouping based on KPIs and EOSC Node association

The current Accounting Service lacks KPI grouping and EOSC Node association, hindering visibility of accounting metrics at a higher organisational level.

To fill this gap the Accounting Service needs to be extended as follows:

- The Accounting Service's schema must be revised to include additional layers in the hierarchy, enabling the flexible grouping of services based on KPIs and Project associations targeted for an EOSC Nodes federation.
- The Accounting Service must enhance its REST API to support the implementation of these new features, enabling seamless access to aggregated statistics, metrics and KPIs for both users and service providers.

ID: WP7-R103, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support grouping of services by KPIs and by EOSC Nodes.

4.3.3. GAP: Report generation per Provider, Service and EOSC Node

The hierarchical structure that embodies the software architecture of the Accounting Service needs to be adjusted to fully accommodate this feature and ensure accurate reporting across all levels.

To facilitate this feature:

- The Accounting Service needs to integrate new REST API calls, allowing users of associated roles (e.g. Service Providers) to access aggregated metrics information.
- The Accounting Service should implement an effective aggregation mechanism for metrics per entity, ensuring that data can be accurately compiled and reported for each individual Provider, Service and federation.
- The sophisticated algorithms are essential to produce accurate aggregated data and handle various metrics aggregation policies.

ID: WP7-R104, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support the creation of reports per Provider, Service, EOSC Node.

4.3.4. GAP: National or Thematic Node integration

The current software architecture of the Accounting Service provides the necessary hooks to implement the report generation functionality. However, the hierarchical structure of the core mechanisms of the Accounting Service must be adjusted to effectively support this national or thematic Node integration.

To facilitate this feature:

- The Accounting Service must gather all the necessary needs to ensure that the new hierarchical structure is adequate for creating national or thematic Node integration.
- To fully support this functionality, several software adjustments may be necessary, including modifications to existing algorithms, enhancements to the REST API calls, and updates to the underlying database structure to ensure seamless integration and optimal performance.

ID: WP7-R105, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Add support for National or Thematic Nodes.

4.3.5. GAP: Improved Reporting: Supporting Various Filters and Criteria

The Accounting Service provides a basic retrieval mechanism for accessing metrics and data; however, it could be enhanced with additional functionalities to improve its reporting capabilities and better support user needs.

To facilitate this feature:

- **Basic Criteria:** Clients should be able to apply basic filters such as time range, service selection, resource type (e.g., CPU, memory, storage, or network bandwidth), geographic location, and user or organisation to analyse specific aspects of their metrics effectively.
- **Advanced Criteria:** Advanced filters could enable clients to select specific usage metrics for analysis, such as CPU utilisation, memory consumption and network traffic, while also allowing them to set thresholds to identify usage anomalies or exceedances.

Therefore, based on the identified needs, various filters from both basic and advanced criteria can be developed and integrated into the Accounting Service depending on the requests.

ID: WP7-R106, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Add Support for reports based on different filters and criteria.

4.3.6. GAP: Capacity management support

Currently, the Accounting Service does not possess the sophistication needed to offer available capacity of consumable services to users. To implement this feature, the

Accounting Service should be able to communicate with external services to gather capacity/quota information relevant to users' service usage, ensuring a thorough understanding of resource consumption. By integrating this quota data with existing metrics, the service would provide users with a comprehensive overview of their usage patterns and resource allocation. Additionally, the system could include mechanisms to alert users when their usage approaches predefined thresholds, enabling effective resource management and helping to prevent unexpected charges or service interruptions.

To facilitate this feature:

- The Accounting Service should be capable of communicating with external services to retrieve quota information related to users' service usage, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of resource consumption.
- Once the quota information is obtained, the Accounting Service should combine this data with existing metrics to provide a holistic view of usage patterns and resource allocation.
- The system should be designed to warn users when their usage approaches predefined thresholds, helping them manage their resources effectively and avoid unexpected charges or service interruptions.

ID: WP7-R107, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Add Support for Capacity management.

4.3.7. GAP: Order management support

The Accounting Service could significantly improve its functionality by associating accounting usage per order per various entities such as Providers, or Installations. This capability would enable service usage linking to provide users with an overall activity within a Project. By integrating this feature, clients would be better equipped to manage resources effectively and make informed decisions based on comprehensive usage data.

To facilitate this feature:

- The internal structure of the Accounting Service must be modified to accommodate accounting usage data at the order level, providing a more granular view of resource consumption and costs.
- More complex internal mechanisms need to be implemented to associate resources with orders.
- New REST API calls are required to enable the export of detailed accounting information associated with specific orders so that clients can retrieve this information.

ID: WP7-R108, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Add Support for Order management.

4.3.8. GAP: Report generation per Project, Provider, Resource, National or Thematic Node

The hierarchical structure within the Accounting Service's software architecture needs to be adjusted to fully support this feature and ensure accurate reporting across all levels.

To enable this functionality:

- The Accounting Service must integrate new REST API calls, allowing users in relevant roles (e.g., Service Providers) to access aggregated metrics data for Projects, Providers, Resources and National or Thematic Nodes.
- An effective aggregation mechanism for metrics per entity should be implemented to ensure that data is accurately compiled and reported for each individual Project, Provider, Resource and Node.
- Sophisticated algorithms are needed to generate precise aggregated data and effectively manage various metrics aggregation policies across different entities and Nodes.
- Federation mechanisms need to be implemented to orchestrate accurately the metrics gathering per National or Thematic Node.

ID: WP7-R109, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Add Support for the creation of reports per Project, Provider, Resource, National or Thematic Node.

4.3.9. GAP: Enhancing EOSC Profiles with Service Accounting Data: Integrating the Resource Catalogue

The Accounting Service is designed to streamline the collection, aggregation and exchange of metrics across various infrastructures, providers and projects. However, it currently lacks integration with the EOSC Service Catalogue, meaning there is no straightforward way to automatically introduce these metrics as extra metadata into the EOSC Profiles for listed services. To enable this functionality:

- The Accounting Service should enhance its integration with the Service catalogue so that there is a clear mapping of the accounting data collected with each onboarded service.
- The EOSC Service Catalogue needs to be updated to accept, display and regularly refresh this accounting metadata, ensuring users can effectively track and visualise their resource usage across projects and services.
- Secure API-level authentication and authorization mechanisms are essential to ensure accurate and private transfer of data between systems, guaranteeing the correct mapping of users to their accounting metrics while maintaining data integrity.

ID: WP7-R9, Requestor: DoA Requirement: Accounting for Services: Integration with the Resource Catalogue to allow accounting data for services to be introduced as extra metadata in the EOSC Profiles.

4.4. Helpdesk

The EOSC Helpdesk is the entry point and ticketing system/request tracker which provides a centralised support service for users across multiple communities and e-infrastructures. The EOSC Helpdesk provides multiple capabilities, such as multiple ticket submission channels, helpdesk portal, reporting and notifications.

The main component of the EOSC Helpdesk is the Helpdesk Back Office that implements the core functionality of the service: ticket management, user role management, management of the support groups, etc.

The Helpdesk portal provides the UI for both users and helpdesk agents, search functionality based on Elasticsearch engine, reporting and statistics dashboards and also knowledge base tightly integrated with the helpdesk.

In the scope of the EOSC Node Federation EOSC Helpdesk offers multiple integration options for EOSC exchange service providers and Pilot Nodes to enable seamless collaboration and support of EOSC federated services.

In the scope of this gap analysis for current EOSC Helpdesk we have identified three major gap categories which are described in detail below.

4.4.1. GAP: Lack of Core Helpdesk Capabilities needed by EOSC

The EOSC Helpdesk is based on the open-source helpdesk software Zammad. Although the Zammad software provides a rich set of features implemented in the helpdesk, it lacks some important features required for efficient support in the EOSC ecosystem.

This gap refers to the absence of these essential features needed to meet EOSC's diverse and growing requirements.

To address this gap:

- The helpdesk will add broadcast functionality to allow instant notifications to particular customizable groups of agents. All broadcast messages are saved in a broadcast history log and can be reused again. The notifications will be sent to agents emails added in the helpdesk without exposing other recipients of the broadcast message.
- The advanced dashboard of ticket states will enable overview of all ticket states in different support groups with instant filtering and access.
- Multiple groups can be involved in the ticket management by helpdesk new functionality which will allow them to subscribe different groups to particular tickets to facilitate collaborative work.

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

- The integration with EOSC Core components will be improved to enable seamless access to support systems from different Core services.

WP7-R128 Requestor: Product team Requirement: Implementation of the broadcast function in the helpdesk to notify any group of users

WP7-R115 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Develop a matrix of ticket states for better ticket tracking and management

WP7-R123 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Subscription and assignment to the ticket by multiple support groups to facilitate collaboration

WP7-R125 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Improve integration with EOSC Core components (Service Provider Dashboard for providers-EPOT team interaction, Marketplace for users-EOSC support group interactions).

WP7-R127 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Helpdesk integrated in EOSC platform to off-the-shelf support EOSC Exchange services;

4.4.2. GAP: Limitation of Helpdesk-as-a-Service Offering

One of the main integration options is the offering of the EOSC Helpdesk as-a-Service for Exchange service providers or any other interested communities. Using this option service providers can directly utilise the EOSC Helpdesk-as-a-Service.

This option allows providers to leverage the existing infrastructure and capabilities of the helpdesk to provide support to their users. Providers can establish their own support group or multiple groups within the helpdesk for their services, aligning with their organisational structure. They can utilise the helpdesk's features, including ticket management, reporting, notifications etc., to efficiently handle user requests.

This gap addresses the constrained functionalities of existing Helpdesk-as-a-Service solution, which was implemented in the EOSC Future project, providing very limited customization necessary for communities to implement their user support processes, and very limited isolation from other community spaces.

In the current implementation of Helpdesk-as-a-Service the agents of one helpdesk community portal can't see the tickets from another portal, but they have full access to the personal information (names, emails) of the agents from other portals and also their users. The customisation of the community portal and user management is also very limited.

To address this gap:

- The delivery of the Helpdesk-as-Service will be enhanced, which will include more customisation options for the communities including mini-admin function, to allow management of the community support agents independently from central administration, access to limited admin settings, like mail filtering, overview management, user management etc.

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

- The Helpdesk Community Portals will be better isolated to comply with security requirements of the communities: agents from one portal won't be able to see agents (names and emails) from other portals if requested.
- The Helpdesk Knowledge Base will be improved by enhancing web UI and implementation of the standalone views in the Multiportal environment for Helpdesk-as-a-Service offering. The communities which use the Helpdesk-as-a-Service will be able to create their own Knowledge Base hierarchies and views.

ID:WP7-R110 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Delivery of Enhanced Helpdesk-as-a-Service

ID:WP7-R112 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Improve management of community users

ID:WP7-R111 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Introduce more custom features

ID:WP7-R113 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Enhance isolation of the helpdesk community space from other spaces within the helpdesk

WP7-R19 Requestor: DoA Requirement: Helpdesk: Helpdesk Knowledge base - enhancement of GUI and implementation of the connection between Knowledge bases in a Multiportal environment.

4.4.3. GAP: Lack of Efficient and Scalable Integration solution for Helpdesks Interconnection

The integrity of the EOSC ecosystem can only be guaranteed if support systems of different EOSC Nodes are integrated and interconnected to each other.

The initial solution offered by the EOSC Future project is built around a helpdesk proxy service that integrates multiple helpdesks and enables bi-directional synchronisation of tickets, creating a unified support network from initially independent helpdesk systems. This allows sharing of tickets across different EOSC helpdesk systems, facilitating collaborative work on user requests. Tickets can be instantly forwarded to the appropriate support entity, regardless of its location within any EOSC Node. The assigned entity manages and resolves the ticket, with the response seamlessly returned to the original requester, ensuring efficient support.

Although the initial solution has been delivered and used to integrate multiple helpdesk systems, we are missing the robust and scalable methods for interconnecting different helpdesks, hindering seamless collaboration and support across platforms.

To address this gap:

- The new proxy service based on the new technology will be deployed and configured.
- The new proxy service will offer a possibility of graphical workflow construction to facilitate the design and preparation phase of integration between helpdesk systems.
- The focus will be given to modular architecture of the integration solution to simplify further development and scalability.

- A simplified configuration and field mapping approach will be provided to helpdesk systems for integration.

ID: WP7-R120 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Pilot integration with NFDI HIFIS Zammad instance based on the new prototype

ID: WP7-R118 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Pilot integration with OpenAIRE based on the new prototype

ID: WP7-R117 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Create a prototype adopters for seamless integration with other Zammad helpdesks and systems

4.5. Interoperability Framework Registry

The EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) Registry, as part of the EOSC Platform, is designed to provide tools for detailing the interoperability capabilities of resources, specifically through Interoperability Guidelines (IG). The registry allows for the annotation of EOSC resources across various research and e-infrastructure domains, indicating the interoperability guidelines they adhere to. It facilitates an interoperability-focused overlay of EOSC resources across diverse disciplines, enabling discovery based on their interoperability capabilities and characteristics.

4.5.1. GAP: Interoperability Registry needs to support machine readable guidelines

The EOSC IF Registry is currently associated with a collection of guidelines that serve as human-readable instructions for EOSC Providers. These guidelines, however essential for enabling specific functionalities and interoperability between EOSC services and research products, are not machine readable. They reference a variety of existing standards, protocols and guidelines (such as FAIRsharing DOIs), and as such:

- Providers need to effectively design and configure their services and spend some time to transform them to technical requirements for their services.
- Software developers must grasp the detailed technical requirements necessary for coding interoperability with these services, and convert human-readable instructions to pieces of code that actually perform the integration.

In a few words, EOSC IF registry entries do not contain detailed and machine-readable metadata that can automate the validation of compatibility and/or possible composability between resources.

On the contrary, EOSC IF Registry should support machine-readable specifications for the composability of resources. To achieve this, the IF Registry needs to store and manage configurations of IF Guidelines in the form of structured metadata profiles, allowing providers to specify the access protocol, the offered functionalities in terms of available API methods, input and output parameters, access policies, pre- or post-call conditions of their services in accordance with the guidelines. With this capability, IF Guideline “owners” can

equip guidelines with custom configuration templates that compliant service providers can fill in to specify the parameters of their services. This will enable a service instance to be de facto 'composable' and 'deployable', based on the characteristics the service owner has provided.

Moreover, Service Providers should have the ability to offer optional (in terms of service definition) software tools in the form of 'adapters' to facilitate the integration of external tools to their services. Adapters need to be a part of the Service Profile definition, in an one-service-to-many adapters relation and to reference an Interoperability Guideline (IG) in the EOSC IF Registry. Seen the other way around, IG entries in the IF Registry should be able to provide reference not only to services declared to comply with them, but also to each service's existing adapters.

ID: WP7-R47, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extend IF Guidelines to comply with TOSCA. Link with Services Adapters

4.6. Marketplace

The EOSC Marketplace service serves as a vital component within the EOSC ecosystem, providing a platform for users to browse, search and purchase a wide array of resources and services. Currently, the marketplace and search functionalities are integrated into a single Marketplace (MP) platform, allowing users to engage with products and services within the same environment. The gap analysis below presents the main challenges to be undertaken in the EOSC Beyond project with highest emphasis on a federated discovery capability (for services and data and other scientific resources) which should be followed by resource composability addressed also in the EOSC Execution Framework Core Service. These two (as one workflow in a federated environment) are highly complex so technological outcomes would rather scope to specific use cases and technologies available in the project. However, the analysis and the design activities for the sake of EOSC Marketplace development in WP8 and WP9 will try to grasp the problem as a whole and plan adequate technical solutions that might be taken and adapted by other EOSC activities considering the federated search challenge.

4.6.1. GAP: Separation of Marketplace into Two Distinct Services - Marketplace and Research Discovery Service

Current State:

The current MP platform combines both Marketplace functionality and search capabilities into a single service. This unified system allows users to browse, search and purchase resources or services. Key Features in the Current System:

1. Integrated marketplace and search functions within one platform.
2. Users can search for products and services, browse listings and make purchases in a single environment.
3. Shared infrastructure and data models for both search and marketplace operations.

Gap Analysis:

The goal is to separate the MP platform into two distinct services:

1. Marketplace Service: Responsible for handling order management
2. Search Service: A dedicated service optimised for advanced search capabilities for all types of resources, allowing users to query, filter results and browse based on specific criteria.

Benefits of Separation:

1. Improved Scalability: Each service can scale independently based on demand. Search functionality, which requires heavy querying and indexing, can be optimised without affecting the marketplace operations.
2. Enhanced Performance: This will result in faster search queries and a more responsive marketplace.
3. User Experience: A dedicated search service will allow for more advanced search filters, recommendations and better search accuracy, improving the overall user experience.
4. Operational Flexibility: Easier maintenance, updates and troubleshooting, as changes to one service (search or marketplace) won't affect the other.

ID: WP7-R131, Requestor: Product Team Requirement: Separation of Marketplace into Two Distinct Services: Marketplace and Research Discovery Service

4.6.2. GAP: EOSC Marketplace for Service Discovery by IF Guidelines, Programming Language, or Platform of Available Integration Libraries

Current State:

1. Basic service discovery functions exist, allowing users to search by service type, discipline, or resource name.
2. Some metadata for services, including documentation links, keywords and relevant categories, are available.
3. The system allows the categorization of services based on certain filters.

Future state/Gaps:

1. Lack of Specific Filters for IF Guidelines: There is no direct filtering mechanism or category that allows users to search for services based on specific Interoperability Framework (IF) Guidelines, limiting the discoverability of services.
2. Programming Language or Platform Filters: The EOSC Marketplace does not currently have filters that allow users to search for services by the programming languages (e.g., Python, Java) or platforms (e.g., Docker, Kubernetes) used by integration libraries. This makes it difficult for users to find tools or services that align with their preferred development environment.
3. Integration Library Information: Metadata or documentation on integration libraries associated with services is sparse, lacking clarity on the availability and compatibility of these libraries with the service offered.

Desired state:

1. Service Discovery by IF Guidelines: Services should be searchable based on IF Guidelines, which would allow researchers and developers to find interoperable and compatible resources more easily.

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

2. Programming Language/Platform-Based Search: The marketplace should include search filters for programming languages and platforms that are associated with the integration libraries of a particular service. This would empower users to quickly find services that can be easily integrated into their existing workflows or development environments.
3. Integration Library Metadata: Clear metadata should be provided on the integration libraries available for each service, including programming language compatibility, platform support and compliance with IF Guidelines.

ID: WP7-R53, WP7-R54, WP7-R55, WP7-R64, WP7-R66, Requestor: D5.1, Requirement: Visual representation of the relationships between EOSC services, IF Guidelines and integration libraries.

4.6.3. GAP: Execution of the e-infra services from a common user space

Current state: users instantiate their services on premises of the providers providing given service

Goal: e-infra resources available in the EOSC Nodes Federation should be executable on the EOSC Level

How: analyse and implement desired user journey (considering the heterogeneous environment in the federation). Integrate with the EOSC Deployment Service (Infrastructure Manager). Align the changes with the EOSC Order Management Service which will be also involved in the underlying user journey.

ID: WP7-R132, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Execution of the e-infra services from a common user space

4.6.4. GAP: Federated Catalogue Implementation

Current State:

At present, the discovery of resources and services within the system is handled through a centralised discovery mechanism, where users access a single, unified marketplace or catalogue to search for offerings across the entire federation.

Gap: The primary gap identified is the transition from a centralised discovery model to a federated marketplace/catalogue.

Key Requirements:

1. Federated Discovery Capability: Users need to see all services and resources available in the federation from their local instance of the marketplace or catalogue, avoiding the current need to access a centralised system.

2. **Marketplace Separation:** The separation of the marketplace and search functionality is a direct consequence of the federated approach. This is a core requirement as it ensures flexibility and modularity in how discovery and transactions are handled.

Solution Outline:

The EOSC Beyond project will deliver a federated marketplace and catalogue solution to a certain level of sophistication. However, it is important to note that due to the complexity of this requirement, further enhancements and refinements will be necessary beyond the initial implementation to fully address all technical and operational challenges.

ID: WP7-R133, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Federated Catalogue Implementation

4.7. Messaging Service

The EOSC ecosystem faces a gap in integrating services and ensuring seamless data exchange, primarily due to the absence of a standardised library of commonly used message types and schemas. This complicates service integration across the ecosystem. The EOSC Messaging Service (EMS) addresses this by providing a library of predefined message formats for essential processes such as data discovery, metadata exchange, and event notifications. This standardisation will streamline service integration, reduce complexity, and improve communication reliability. Furthermore, EMS will function as an added-value data transport layer, bridging communication between the EOSC Core, EOSC Exchange services, and various National or Thematic EOSC Nodes, ensuring efficient and standardised data transfer. To enhance the usability of the service, a user interface (UI) will be developed, enabling users to easily access and utilise the main functionalities of EMS.

4.7.1. GAP: A library of commonly used data

In the EOSC environment, many services seek to integrate with others in a way that is transparent, fully automated and consistent. This need for smooth interaction between diverse systems is the main goal of EOSC Messaging Service (EMS), which aims to streamline these integrations by standardising how data is structured, transmitted and understood across the ecosystem. The main goal of EMS is the main transport layer to provide a library of commonly used message types and schemas that define how data should be structured and exchanged. This includes data and formats for data discovery, metadata exchange, event notifications and other critical operations.

EMS simplifies the process of integrating services but also enhances the overall reliability and efficiency of communication within the EOSC. By providing a standardised messaging framework, it can reduce the complexity and effort required to integrate new services, as developers can rely on predefined formats and protocols. This speeds up the deployment of new functionalities and services within the EOSC infrastructure. Services can interact with each other in a transparent and automated manner, eliminating the need for manual data handling or custom integrations. At the same time it facilitates Interoperability with

standardised schemas and message types which ensure that services can interpret and utilise data uniformly, regardless of the originating platform or technology.

EMS could also act as an added-value data transport layer that bridges the communication gap between the EOSC Core, EOSC Exchange services and the various National or Thematic EOSC Nodes. By serving as an intermediary, EMS enables efficient, standardised and secure data transfer between these distinct layers of the EOSC ecosystem.

ID: WP7-R98 , Requestor: Subtask T8.5.2 Requirement: EOSC Messaging: The EOSC Messaging Service (EMS) will fill the gap to the end to end integration between services, by providing a library of commonly used message data.

ID: WP7-R99 , Requestor: Subtask T8.5.2 Requirement: An added-value data transport layer between the EOSC Core and EOSC exchange services and the EOSC Core and National or Thematic EOSC Nodes.

ID:WP7-R97, Requestor: Subtask T8.5.2 Requirement: Act as transport layer/integration point of data between the EOSC Core and EOSC exchange services.

4.7.2. GAP: UI to support the basic functions of messaging

The EOSC Messaging Service (EMS) is a real-time messaging platform that facilitates communication between independent applications by allowing users to send and receive messages using a Publish/Subscribe model over HTTP. While EMS provides an HTTP API for managing entities and accessing operational and statistical metrics, a key gap is the lack of a user interface (UI) to support its basic functions. This includes the need for UIs that allow users to customize and manage essential components such as users, topics, subscriptions, message structures, and schemas. To address this, the EOSC Beyond project aims to develop a UI that will enable easier customization of the core elements of the messaging service, thereby defining a specific service-to-service message transport layer and enhancing user interaction with the EMS.

ID: WP7-R100 , Requestor: Subtask T8.5.2 Requirement: Providing UIs to customise a messaging framework (users, topics, subscriptions, message structure, schemas) to define a specific service-to-service message transport layer.

4.7.3. GAP: Contracts for message exchange

Adding support for contracts that define message schemas and activity metrics in a real-time data exchange system ensures data integrity, reliability, security and predictability. It helps maintain the overall health of the system, facilitates integration with new services and makes debugging and monitoring significantly easier. This is essential for maintaining a robust, scalable and high-performing system in complex environments like the EOSC Exchange services.

Implementing contracts for schema validation and activity monitoring in real-time data exchange systems brings significant benefits by defining and enforcing the structure, content and behaviour of messages exchanged between components. By validating message schemas, the system ensures that only well-formed and complete data is processed, reducing the risk of errors propagating through the system. Activity constraints, such as message frequency, size and throughput limits, prevent resource overuse, protect against performance degradation and maintain system stability. These contracts enable clear communication standards between services, ensuring smooth interoperability and simplifying integration efforts.

Additionally, contracts offer a reliable framework for monitoring and alerting, allowing for early identification of anomalies, such as sudden spikes or drops in message volume and providing a basis for automated error handling and self-healing mechanisms. This approach makes the system more predictable and maintainable by establishing clear expectations, facilitating troubleshooting and enabling backward-compatible versioning for evolving systems. In complex environments like the EOSC Exchange services, contracts ensure that both data and performance standards are consistently met, supporting scalability and future growth while minimising risk and enhancing overall operational resilience.

ID: WP7-R101, Requestor: Subtask T8.5.2 Requirement: Adding support for users to define contracts about messages expected to arrive (schemas validation), expected activity (frequency and size of messages etc). Definition of a contract for exchanging Real Time data between Core components and EOSC Exchange services.

4.8. Monitoring Service

EOSC Monitoring is a well established service that is needed to gain insights into EOSC Services. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour. The challenge of this type of monitoring is how to quickly identify and correlate problems before they affect end-users and ultimately the productivity of the organisation. Management teams can monitor the availability and reliability of the services from a high level view down to individual system metrics and monitor the conformance of multiple SLAs. While EOSC Monitoring offers a number of interoperability options that cover most of the use cases it is clear that the process to integrate with the service needs to be simplified and automated as much as possible. This process should also address the possibility of Nodes to both use EOSC Monitoring as a service or to integrate their own equivalent service so as to be able to exchange data.

4.8.1. GAP: Monitoring as a service (MaaS)

While the Monitoring service has support for multi-tenancy and offers a number of integration options already, that provide a baseline of capabilities to be offered as a Service in order to support EOSC nodes. Quite a few manual steps need to be taken which makes it non-scalable in the long run. In the end a semi-automated workflow should be provided where each node should be able to provide the necessary information to request for a

tenant to be-created for it including its own reports, web ui and status pages. This gap is captured in the following requirements

ID: WP7-R85, Requestor: D5.1 Add support for EOSC Nodes to create their Status Pages.

ID: WP7-R89, Requestor: D5.1 Automate the creation of monitoring instances/tenants to be offered as a service.

ID: WP7-R96, Requestor: D5.1 Add support for National or Thematic EOSC Nodes to create their Status Pages.

4.8.2. GAP: Tighter integration with Service Registry and Profiles is required in order to better Insights of the services available including performance metrics.

While EOSC monitoring offers valuable info for each individual service offered this is beneficial for each service provider but may be confusing for the end User. It has been identified that the users would benefit if monitoring is more tightly integrated with both the Marketplace and The service catalogue as they will be able search and view trends and better Insights of the services available. Monitoring should benefit from this tighter integration by being able to receive valuable metadata for each service so as to be able to correlate trends and classify or group services with different views. Furthermore Monitoring should be extended to allow the definition of new metrics via a semi-automated mechanism so that more detailed checks are performed on each service including performance measurements. This gap is captured in the following requirements.

ID: WP7-R82, Requestor: D5.1 Extend the Monitoring Integration Profiles with service properties that enable richer monitoring reports.

ID: WP7-R83, Requestor: D5.1 Support integration of monitoring data as part of service profiles in the Service Catalogue, for reuse across Core components.

ID: WP7-R84, Requestor: D5.1 Enable the definition of new monitoring metrics by the providers.

ID: WP7-R86, Requestor: D5.1 Extend the Monitoring Integration Profiles (Monitoring Extensions), with additional fields like extra service description that will add extra Business Value based on the functionalities of the service. This will bring trends and better Insights of the service.

ID: WP7-R87, Requestor: D5.1 Automate procedure for the definition of new metrics to be included by the providers.

ID: WP7-R90, Requestor: D5.1 Automate the generation of Status reports based on filters; Create combined Status Reports based on filters, criteria that help users identify the status of the services.

ID: WP7-R92, Requestor: D5.1 Add “badges” for services based on monitoring status reports.

ID: WP7-R93, Requestor: D5.1 Monitoring of service performance.

4.8.3. GAP: Add support for validation and auditing of profiles

A number of processes such as the onboarding process, AAI integration and Security process would benefit from a compliance auditing workflow that can be enabled via Monitoring. This gap is captured in the following requirements

ID: WP7-R88, , Requestor: D5.1 Verify compliance auditing on various areas (e.g. Security, Profiles, AAI).

ID: WP7-R91, , Requestor: D5.1 Add support for the validation of compliance of members of the AAI federation.

ID: WP7-R94, , Requestor: D5.1 Investigate the possibility to Automate the validation and auditing of EOSC Profiles: Monitoring will be the service to validate and audit the profiles according to prerequisites for the onboarding process and after the process to check the status of onboarding service.

4.9. Order Management

The EOSC Order Management service plays a crucial role within the EOSC ecosystem by facilitating the management of resource orders. While the current system effectively handles non-consumable resources, it lacks the capabilities needed for managing consumable resources. At present, the system provides basic resource management and order tracking, with a user interface designed primarily around non-consumable items.

4.9.1. GAP: Asking for resources in a way that easily allows their consumption: introduction of consumable resources

Current State:

The existing Order Management system handles resources order management but there is no possibility to manage consumable resources effectively. The current system supports basic resource management and order tracking. The user interface is built around non-consumable items. System needs significant enhancements to support consumable resources.

Gaps/Future State:

The goal is to extend the current Order Management UIs and back-ends to introduce functionality for consumable resources. This would allow for dynamic tracking and

management of resources that are consumed, enhanced UIs allowing users to configure, monitor and manage orders involving consumable resources. The current UI will have to be extended to include new modules for consumable resource management. These interfaces should provide clear visibility into resource consumption and stock level.

ID: WP7-R15, Requestor: DoA Requirement: Extended Order Management UIs and Back-ends: Order Management interfaces and back-end systems will be enhanced to introduce consumable resources.

4.9.2. GAP: Lack of the integration of the service accounting

To facilitate one of the aspects of a full support for the consumable resources in the order management service, a possibility to integrate it with the EOSC service accounting will be pursued. It's important to understand that service accounting has a heterogeneous nature, due to the technical heterogeneity and different operational strategies for accounting of services. In EOSC Beyond one of the accounting use cases will be depicted for analysis and possible integration with the EOSC Order Management service.

ID: WP7-R134, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Integration of the service accounting

4.10. PID Service

The EOSC ecosystem faces several challenges regarding the integration and management of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and machine-readable type descriptions. Currently, resources are inconsistently defined across platforms, and there is no dedicated PID service, making it difficult to assign and manage PIDs throughout the research lifecycle. To address these issues, solutions such as the implementation of a distributed PID infrastructure (B2HANDLE), the development of an EOSC Core adapter for seamless integration, and better support for custom PID namespaces are proposed. Additionally, creating machine-readable schemas for resources and storing them in a centralised Data Type Registry (DTR) will improve interoperability and automation. These efforts aim to enhance the discoverability, reliability, and integration of research resources within EOSC, ensuring a more efficient and consistent data management system.

4.10.1. GAP: Effective Accounting for PID Services

To establish effective accounting of the PID Service in the EOSC ecosystem via the EOSC Accounting for Services, it is crucial to define the key metrics that should be collected. Currently there is no way to get quantitative data for the PIDs used in the EOSC Ecosystem. Metrics are essential for accounting because they provide quantitative data that helps in measuring the usage of the Service in general and per provider. The first step is to define the Key Metrics to be collected for effective accounting. At the same time a mechanism should be set up to gather and aggregate these metrics across the different prefixes used and the different providers that are offering the EOSC PID service.

Finally, all the required mechanisms for effective Data Transfer and Reporting to the EOSC Accounting Service should be established. The interoperability guidelines of the EOSC Accounting Service and the documentation of standardised protocol REST API will be followed to periodically transfer the collected metrics in an automated way.

ID: WP7-R74 , Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Accounting for PIDs, create the necessary metrics to provide to the Accounting Service and the process to provide the data.

4.10.2. GAP: Lack of machine readable type descriptions, posing challenges in environments that rely on automated resource management and data interoperability

In the EOSC ecosystem, various resources are available to support the research lifecycle and facilitate daily tasks. The integration of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) has enhanced this process, particularly for automating workflows within systems. However, despite PIDs being a key element for achieving interoperability, several challenges persist. Resources are inconsistently defined across different platforms and systems, lacking a standardised approach to describing their properties, metadata, or relationships. Furthermore, existing schemas for resource types are often fragmented, inadequately documented, or maintained manually.

Creating machine-readable type descriptions for supported resources helps establish a consistent method for identifying and accessing resources across different platforms, systems and namespaces. This approach is particularly valuable in complex environments which pose significant challenges in environments that rely on automated resource management and data interoperability systems need to understand and interact with resources programmatically. By combining persistent identifiers (PIDs) with structured, machine-readable type descriptions, resources can be uniquely and consistently defined, enabling seamless integration and management. The initial step is to define a schema for each supported resource type. These schemas specify the properties, metadata and relationships of the resources, providing a standardised format that machines can interpret.

To ensure these schemas are easily accessible, they can be stored in a centralised service like a Data Type Registry (DTR). A DTR serves as a repository where schemas and type descriptions are registered and maintained. It acts as a reference for other services, enabling them to retrieve and utilise type descriptions as needed. By storing type descriptions in a DTR, the system ensures that different services and tools have a unified source of truth, facilitating higher levels of interoperability and machine actionability in managing structured research data.

This approach not only simplifies resource management and discovery but also enables automated systems to perform complex operations—such as searching, validating, or transforming resources—based on well-defined, machine-readable schemas and identifiers. This leads to more efficient data handling, reduced errors and improved consistency across different systems and workflows.

The FAIR Digital Object (FDO) model provides a framework for making digital objects more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). By bundling a digital object (such as a dataset, software, or research paper) with its metadata and a unique identifier, an FDO creates a standardised and structured digital entity. To efficiently process large volumes of FDOs (for instance, research data), automated parsing is essential. For such machine actionability, it is vital to define and associate types to the objects. A set of essential metadata (e.g. PID Kernel Information Profiles⁵) can be linked to PIDs to facilitate the discovery, access and reuse of associated digital objects. Aligning PIDs with the FDO concept is critical in this regard to support the utilisation of standardised, unique and easily discoverable types.

ID: WP7-R76, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Creation of machine readable type descriptions for supported resources.

ID: WP7-R79, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Align PIDs with the FDO concept and model.

4.10.3. GAP: No service to assign and resolve PIDs

Currently, no PID service exists in EOSC to address the need for Persistent Identifiers in EOSC. This hinders the assignment of PIDs for various scientific artefacts throughout the whole research process and data lifecycle. A flexible PID service infrastructure, which is based on the Handle System, will be used in order to support the data life cycle. This service is B2HANDLE⁶, which provides a distributed service for storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers and essential metadata (PID records). The implementation of the service relies on the DONA/Handle⁷ persistent identifier solution. It can be used by middleware applications, end-user tools and other services to reliably identify data objects over longer time spans and through changes in object location or ownership. The service encompasses utilisation of identifier namespaces (Handle prefixes), establishment of policies and business workflows, operation of Handle servers and technical services and a user-friendly Python and/or Java library for general interaction with Handle servers. The service is transparent to end-users, shielding them from the complexity of infrastructure details.

ID: WP7-R73 , Requestor: DoA Requirement: PID Service: PID service to assign and resolve PIDs for providers/resources onboarded into Resource Catalogue.

⁵ A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) - <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/35c5ca10-1417-11eb-b57e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> . The PID Kernel Information Profile describes the set of kernel attributes that are being selected by a repository to describe the DO. The profile is dependent on the type of object and the needs of the community. Only openly declared attributes with widely agreed semantic types will provide machine actionability.

⁶ <https://eudat.eu/service-catalogue/b2handle>

⁷ <https://www.dona.net/>

4.10.4. GAP: Lack of a common interface to integrate with the PID service.

The PID service offers a well-documented API with functionalities that support the full lifecycle of data management, along with libraries to facilitate integration. Beyond the technical integration, the adapter should ensure that PIDs conform to the ecosystem standards, to community standards and use appropriate data exchange mechanisms, considering metadata standards.

The development of an EOSC Core adapter for the PID service involves creating an interface that enables seamless communication between the PID service and EOSC Core components, such as catalogues, using standardised protocols and APIs. In order to create a usable adaptor, different use cases will be followed so as to create a list of requirements. This ensures reliable identification, resolution and management of research outputs. By supporting operations like PID creation, updating and resolution, the adapter enhances the discoverability and accessibility of research resources within the EOSC ecosystem, promoting efficient data management and reuse.

ID: WP7-R77 , Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Development of a EOSC Core adapter for the PID Service.

4.10.5. GAP: PID Service: support for custom PID namespaces.

Each persistent identifier, as used in EOSC Beyond, consists of two parts: a *prefix* (also known as a namespace) and a *suffix*. For example, '12345/abc' has '12345' as the prefix (or namespace) and 'abc' as the suffix. The prefix allows organisations, institutions, or communities to control a specific set of persistent identifiers within that namespace. Each suffix must be unique under its local identifier space. The combination of a unique prefix and suffix under that prefix ensures that each persistent identifier is unique. Furthermore, the prefix also serves as the entity where *technical service parameters* are configured. This technical information is needed for the clients, so that they are able to locate the responsible server(s) and can deal with identifier resolution requests or administer identifiers under the prefix.

Key technical parameters in the namespace include:

- Service details, such as IP address, port and trusted certificates
- Permissions, such as the ability to create identifiers under the prefix or the permission to list identifiers under the prefix.

The PID Service is a decentralised system for minting and managing unique identifiers. Because of the decentralised nature of the service, a coordinated assignment and management of namespaces is necessary to ensure this uniqueness (similar to the controlled assignment of domain names).

Also the maintenance of the technical parameters has limitations in the current system. Service administrators cannot update their technical parameters independently and instead rely on global administrators to make changes in the namespace configurations manually. This process can be time-consuming and does not scale well. More support (e.g. tooling) for maintaining PID namespaces is required.

ID: WP7-R13 , Requestor: DoA Requirement: Support for custom PID namespaces.

4.10.6. GAP: Lack of a persistent identification system for scientific instruments for specific communities.

In many EOSC communities, there's a substantial need for a persistent identification system for scientific instruments. These instruments - including sensors, DNA sequencers, microscopes and others - are crucial in numerous fields, such as environmental science, life sciences and medical sectors. Previous initiatives have made some progress towards addressing this need of the research communities and individual researchers to describe, register and refer to their instruments.

The most significant of these solutions is the B2INST⁸ service. B2INST is an emerging service for registering scientific instruments. Its main objective is to offer a global and unique identification system that can be used universally in the research communities. By integrating the B2INST service into EOSC, researchers will be able to assign Persistent Identifiers to their instruments, ensuring that they adhere to standards endorsed by the research community.

4.10.7. GAP: Check the Quality of Prefixes and PIDs used

PID prefixes contain technical parameters that define the service instances responsible for PID resolution requests or identifier administration under the prefix. These service instances can be primary (for maintenance) or mirror (for backup and/or additional resolution). A basic PID service setup typically consists of a single primary instance only, but the EOSC Beyond PID providers have implemented a more robust and reliable replication procedure. This involves a primary server storing PID records and one or more mirror servers replicating the records from the primary server. The mirror instances are used transparently for resolution, providing redundancy, a full backup of all PIDs and disaster recovery capabilities.

To ensure the integrity of the PID infrastructure, each PID service instance responsible for a particular prefix must be registered with the Global Handle Registry. This involves adding a specific parameter to the prefix, which contains technical information for clients on how to reach the PID service instances. The registered information in the registry and the current status of the service instances must match. Otherwise, the integrity of the PID infrastructure could not be guaranteed.

⁸ <https://docs.eudat.eu/b2inst/>

It is therefore required that the integrity of the PID infrastructure is periodically checked, and the status should be easily understandable to users. This transparent view of PID integrity can serve as a basis for future certification of PID services.

4.11. Service Registry

The EOSC Service Registry provides data and functionality to register, maintain, administer and share resources onboarded by various providers. It also serves as the point of reference for all EOSC Core components that add value to this information, making the data and services searchable and accessible through various tools for both researchers and end users.

4.11.1. GAP: Service Catalogue needs to be offered as a deployable service

Service Catalogue needs to be offered as a deployable service in order to provide a tested and complete registry for all those seeking to create curated collections of services offered to researchers. It also needs to easily integrate with other EOSC Core Services (such as Monitoring, Helpdesk, etc.) in the context of an EOSC Node infrastructure.

To cover this, the Service Registry should offer 'deployment as a service' or as a deployable package for EOSC Nodes. This includes ensuring local instances feature off-the-shelf integration with EOSC AAI, EOSC PID Service and EOSC Messaging Service. Listing and linking to resources in other EOSC Node instances highlighting the Resource Profile version used is also required.

ID: WP7-R131, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Deployable Service Catalogue: Finalisation of the Service Catalogue for EOSC Nodes (aaS, deployable service), ensuring local instances feature an off-the-shelf integration with EOSC AAI, EOSC PID service, and EOSC Messaging Service. Listing and linking to Resources in other EOSC Node instances highlighting the Resource Profile version used.

4.11.2. GAP: Support of different service types

The Service Catalogue needs to support different 'flavours' of services to match the need for a diverse set of service types. Although steps have been made in this direction, with the introduction of the notion of a service subprofile, current subprofiles of services are limited to just datasources, This needs to be extended to other types of services, such as computing services, deployable services, training resources, service aggregators etc.

To cover this, the Service Registry should offer a specialisation of service types. This includes support for Profile evolution: Specialisation of service types to include more specific properties (datasource, computing services, deployable services). Also, the ability to adapt to resource profile changes should be included.

ID: WP7-R130, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for Profile evolution: Specialisation of service types to include more specific properties (datasource, computing services, deployable services). Ability to adapt to resource profile changes.

4.11.3. GAP: PID support through the EOSC PID Service

PID minting has been implemented as a standalone service in the Service Catalogue for assigning PIDs to newly onboarded services. However, the federated nature of the EOSC Nodes could potentially allow that different PIDs are assigned to the same service. Thus, the use of a central EOSC PID service can avoid duplicate PIDs and ensure the consistency of the resource IDs across different EOSC Nodes.

To cover this gap, Service Registry should assign PIDs to onboarded resources via the EOSC PID service.

ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC PID service. Integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc).

4.11.4. GAP: Service deduplication

Services are rarely onboarded to a single Catalogue or Node; multiple appearances of the same service can be found across regional and thematic catalogues. Tools are needed to avoid duplicates of the same service in Service Registry listings.

To cover this gap, service profile deduplication support for the onboarding team operations will be implemented.

ID: WP7-R4, Requestor: DoA Service catalogue: support to service profile deduplication, enhanced integration with EOSC Core components, EOSC Execution Framework (EF), and EOSC Integration Suite (IS). Service Catalogue offered aaS/deployable.

4.11.5. GAP: Integration with other EOSC Core components

The Service Registry needs to integrate with other EOSC Core components, such as AAI, Marketplace, Monitoring, Helpdesk and Accounting in a more seamless way. Onboarding now requires service owners to enter their service information to take advantage of functionality offered by other core components; this should be done in a more unified and automated way.

To cover this gap, the Service Registry should offer improved integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc).

ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC

PID service. Integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc.

4.11.6. GAP: Use of a common communication channel across EOSC Core Components

Integration with a common channel for events and messaging across EOSC Core Components is required to avoid one-to-one integrations and to facilitate seamless communication with upcoming EOSC Core Components.

For this gap, use of EOSC Messaging mechanism should be adopted

ID: WP7-R43, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Extending Integration Capabilities: Use of EOSC Messaging Service to integrate with EOSC Core components, support PIDs via EOSC PID service. Integration with other EOSC Core Components (Monitoring, Accounting, Helpdesk, etc.

4.11.7. GAP: Support IF adapters and IG configuration templates

Service Catalogue needs to support optional software libraries (adapters) offered for integration by the Service Owners. Also, Service Owners should be able to define configuration parameters for their services to be offered as deployable instances and to be able to support composability with other services which support integration.

To cover this gap, the Service Registry will offer TOSCA⁹ Deployable Services support: the Service Registry should include the ability for Providers to onboard a TOSCA-based deployable release of their services, compatible with the EOSC Deployment Service.

ID: WP7-R132, Requestor: D5.1 TOSCA Deployable Services support: Include the ability for Providers to onboard a TOSCA-based deployable release of their services, compatible with the EOSC Deployment Service

4.12. User Dashboard

The User Dashboard, introduced as a new Core Service in the EOSC Future project, serves as a dedicated, personalised space within the EOSC Platform. It was developed in response to researchers' needs for a platform akin to a social network, where the scientists can exchange ideas, seek consultancy and foster new collaborations—all under the paradigm of open science and scientific open data management.

Initially, the User Dashboard was not planned for further development in the EOSC Beyond project, as its main goals did not align with this service. Consequently, there are no specific requirements related to it in the project's Description of Action (DoA). However, findings from the requirement gathering process involving Pilot Nodes and the gap analysis—especially

⁹ OASIS Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) TC <https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tosca/faq.php>

concerning usability and discoverability—highlight the potential benefits of its continued development within EOSC Beyond, provided adequate resources are available. If further development is not feasible, EOSC Beyond will forward these requirements to other projects with goals similar to those of the EOSC User Dashboard.

4.12.1. GAP: Lack of Diverse Content and Absence of Frequently Updated Content

The current system does not offer a wide variety of content, which limits user engagement and the richness of the platform. Diverse content is crucial to cater to different user interests and needs, ensuring that users find value in returning and exploring the platform regularly.

There is a lack of frequently changing or dynamic content that would encourage users to return to their dashboard more often. Introducing time-sensitive or trending material can significantly boost user engagement and create a habit of frequent visits, ultimately enhancing platform loyalty.

There is also no current mechanism for users to publish posts or share updates directly within the platform. Adding this functionality would empower users to actively participate, share knowledge and build a sense of community, making the platform more interactive and engaging.

ID: WP7-R134, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Enhanced Integration for an Enriched User Experience

4.12.2. GAP: Limited User Profile Customisation

The current user profile is minimalistic and lacks options for users to expand or enrich their profiles. This limitation restricts users from showcasing their expertise, achievements and interests comprehensively.

Introduce more customisation options for user profiles, allowing users to add detailed information about their skills, experiences, projects and achievements. By providing richer profile fields and customisation tools, a more engaging and informative user experience will be created, enabling users to fully express their professional and personal identities on the platform. These updates will implement designs inspired by the users' feedback from the EOSC Future initiative, ensuring that the changes meet user needs and preferences while adhering to the latest standards.

ID: WP7-R135, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: User Profile Update

4.12.3. GAP: No Option for Collaboration Initiatives

The platform lacks a feature which enables inviting users to collaborate, such as sharing projects in the Marketplace. Enabling this function would foster a collaborative environment, allowing users to engage and co-create more effectively, which aligns with the platform's goals of supporting scientific and project-based collaboration.

A collaboration invitation system is planned that allows users to invite others to join projects, share resources and collaborate within the Marketplace. This feature will support co-creation

and teamwork, aligning with the platform's objective of fostering collaborative environments for scientific and professional growth.

ID: WP7-R136, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Collaboration Initiatives

4.12.4. GAP: No User Discovery Feature

Users currently do not have a way to find or connect with other users on the platform. Implementing a feature that allows for user discovery can promote collaboration, networking and community building, which are essential for enhancing the overall user experience and engagement.

ID: WP7-R137, Requestor: Product Team, Requirement: Better User Discovery Feature

4.13. Providers' Dashboard

The EOSC Service Providers' Dashboard enables the front-end functionality for the registration of EOSC Providers (organisations entitled to publish their resources via the EOSC Catalogue) and offers them capabilities to onboard and manage EOSC resources.

4.13.1. GAP: Providers Dashboard adaptation to new profile specifications

For each new profile specification (or alteration to an existing profile specification), the Providers' Dashboard needs to implement additions and updates. This takes a lot of time. A UI is necessary to be able to adopt changes in profiles by auto-consuming specifications.

ID: WP7-R130, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Support for Profile evolution: Specialisation of service types to include more specific properties (datasource, computing services, deployable services). Ability to adapt to resource profile changes

4.13.2. GAP: UI/UX redesign

The Providers' Dashboard needs to update its UI/UX experience for service owners, to become more eye-appealing and easier to onboard services. Also, Providers should now be able to use the new Service Registry features, such as association of services with adapters and configuration templates for service deployable instances.

For both gaps mentioned above, the Providers' Dashboard should offer a redesigned UI/UX for uniform resource onboarding procedure across all different types of resources; UIs are to be adaptable to resource profile changes. Also, regarding the onboarding procedure, ability for service owners to upload adapters for interoperability will be implemented. Service owners should be able to use the UI to define configuration templates for their deployable service instances.

ID: WP7-R6 Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Service Providers Dashboard: redesigned UI/UX for uniform resource onboarding procedure across all different types of resources; UIs adaptable to resource profile changes.

4.13.3. GAP: Assistance tools for Providers

Providers should have access to tools and statistics regarding their onboarded services.

For this, assistance tools should be implemented; these are tools that will be used for Providers onboarding and advanced insights and analytics for their service portfolio across EOSC Nodes.

ID: WP7-R51, Requestor: D5.1 Requirement: Assistance tools: Tools for Providers onboarding and advanced insights and analytics for their service portfolio across EOSC Nodes

5. Conclusions

This initial report presents the detailed process of gathering and analysing requirements to improve the existing European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Core services, which are a key focus of the EOSC Beyond project. The objective is to ensure these services evolve to meet the changing needs of stakeholders, including end-users, service providers. The EOSC Core platform needs also to evolve to support a federation of national, regional and thematic EOSC Nodes which implies that most of the capabilities that are part of EOSC core will need to be either easy to deploy or offered as a service. Furthermore it is clear that the end users will benefit from a more coherently integrated EOSC Core platform that supports their needs. So far we have identified over 50 gaps that are in turn analysed to over 70 requirements to be translated to specifications. The requirements analysis process will continue as part of WP7, with a final report to be delivered toward the end of the work package. This will serve as a handoff to WP8 and WP9, ensuring the ongoing development and improvement of each service and the EOSC Core Platform as a whole. The goal is to continuously address the evolving needs of stakeholders, including end-users, service providers, and EOSC Nodes.

Capability	Requirements	Gaps
AAI	5	5
Accounting for research products	3	2
Accounting for services	9	9
Helpdesk	13	3
Interoperability Framework registry	1	1
Marketplace	4	4
Messaging Service	5	3
Monitoring	14	3
Order Management	2	2
PID Service	9	6
Provider Dashboard	3	3
Resource Catalogue	1	6
Service Catalogue	7	7
User Dashboard	4	4
Grand Total	80	58

6. Acronyms

Term	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
aaS	as a Service
API	Application Programming Interface
CIS	Core Innovation Sandbox
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DNS	Domain Name System
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EF	Execution Framework (EOSC)
EMS	EOSC Messaging Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
IF	Interoperability Framework
IS	Integration Suite
IG	Interoperability Guidelines
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MFA	Multi Factor Authentication
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenID	Open standard and decentralised authentication protocol
PID	Persistent Identifier
SaaS	Service as a Service
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SCIM	System for Cross-domain Identity Management
SIMPL	An open source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces.
SSO	Single Sign On
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications

Appendix 1

Appendix 1 summarises the high-level requirements of EOSC Beyond's Pilot Nodes and identifies potential functional and technical gaps related to the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox.

EGI Node

Requirements:

- Federated storage and computing services.
- Integration with AAI, order management and service catalogue.
- Resource orchestration and automated deployment.
- Monitoring and synchronisation with the EU Node.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Potential gaps in ensuring interoperability and composability between EGI's local services and the EOSC Core services, especially in the areas of resource allocation and monitoring.
- Challenges may arise in automating workflows for scaling resources across multiple Nodes.
- Limited user training and support for service tools.

CESSDA Node

Requirements:

- Seamless access to and tracking of resource usage.
- Reliable PID registration and resolution services.
- Single Sign-On access through federated AAI.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Integration between CESSDA's services and EOSC accounting and monitoring services might present challenges.
- Compatibility and management of AAI across institutions.
- Technical challenges in integrating PID services with existing infrastructure.

CNB-CSIC Node

Requirements:

- Cloud-based validation services for cryo-EM research.
- Federated data access and integration with cryo-EM repositories.
- Automated cloud deployment for periodic validation updates.
- Support for file transfer and resource allocation through the EOSC Execution Framework.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

- Resource limitations (e.g., GPUs, storage) for validation.
- Data management and compatibility between tools.
- Challenges in automating periodic updates to validation repositories.

Instruct ERIC Node

Requirements:

- Long-term storage solutions with accurate metadata management.
- Ability to provide proper public access with controlled data release.
- PID integration to track and link research outputs.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Reliable and transparent storage setups.
- Secure data management and release after embargo periods.
- Challenges in accurate tracking of research outputs using PIDs.

e-INFRA CZ Node

Requirements:

- Integration of local AAI with EOSC AAI for cross-border collaboration.
- Secure data handling and sharing across Nodes.
- Scientific service registration and visibility in resource catalogues.
- Provision of a notebook service that allows data storage, analysis and sharing across Nodes.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Secure data transfer and sharing across Nodes.
- Complexity in synchronising data transfer services between national Nodes and EOSC services.
- Scalability challenges for supporting cross-Node execution of notebooks and workflows

ENES Node

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for secure access to computing resources.
- Cloud-based orchestration services for climate data analysis.
- Federated catalogues for data visibility and accessibility.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Resource limitations for big data processing and cloud computing.
- Integration challenges for data science tools with federated resources.
- Synchronisation of data collections across federated catalogues.

NFDI Node

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for flexible identity management.
- Secure access management for shared resources.
- Unique user identification across sessions.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in managing AAI across different institutions.
- Integration challenges with multiple identity providers.
- Difficulty in ensuring accurate user tracking for personalised services.

LifeWatch Node

Requirements:

- Federated metadata catalogues for ecosystem evaluation.
- High FAIR compliance and secure data backup for research activities.
- Integration of Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in integrating catalogues with EOSC resources.
- Availability and retrieval of specific datasets.
- Consistent monitoring of FAIR principles for metadata.
- Challenges in managing ticketing and helpdesk support across multiple Nodes.

NI4OS Node

Requirements:

- Federated AAI for accessing research services.
- Cloud resources and thematic service catalogues.
- Integration with APIs for research simulations and climate data.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in integrating AAI and cloud resources.
- Harmonising thematic service APIs and cloud resources with EOSC standards.
- Challenges in federating access to climate research datasets.

METROFOOD Node

Requirements:

- Simplified single sign-on with federated AAI.
- Integration of METROFOOD catalogues with EOSC.
- Federated helpdesk services for user support.

Potential functional and technical gaps:

- Complexity in AAI integration for unified SSO.
- Ensuring FAIR data principles are fully met within METROFOOD's catalogues.

D7.1 Initial EOSC Core Gap Analysis and Requirements Report

- Integration issues with EOSC helpdesk services.